

TENANT: a Tool for Easily Modeling Task Planning Problems for Human-Robot Collaboration

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Abstract—For an effective deployment in manufacturing, Collaborative Robots should be capable of adapting their behavior to the state of the environment and to keep the user safe and engaged during the interaction. Artificial Intelligence (AI) enables robots to autonomously operate understanding the environment, planning their tasks and acting to achieve some given goals. However, the effective deployment of AI technologies in real industrial environments is not straightforward. There is a need for *engineering tools* facilitating communication and interaction between AI engineers and Domain experts. This paper presents a novel software tool, called TENANT (Tool foStEriNg Ai plaNning in roboTics) whose aim is to facilitate the use of AI planning technologies by providing domain experts like e.g., production engineers, with a graphical software framework to synthesize AI planning models abstracting from syntactic features of the underlying planning formalism. This work was presented during the 30th IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN 2021).

Index Terms—component, formatting, style, styling

I. INTRODUCTION

The deployment of Human-Robot Collaborative (HRC) Robots in manufacturing scenarios requires to address multiple challenges. It is of paramount importance to endow cobots with the ability of quickly adapting behaviours to actual state of the environment and to keep the user safe and engaged during the interaction. Long-term research activities are ongoing to enable robots to autonomously operate in environments, i.e., understanding the actual situation, planning their tasks and acting to safely and effectively achieve some given goals [1]. Several approaches aim to achieve robust action selection via Artificial Intelligence (AI) Planning, e.g., [2]–[4] or robust execution via some form of finite state machine (FSM), e.g., [5], [6]. The development of tools that facilitate the integration (and interaction) of AI planning and robotics entails different skills that are all necessary to effectively address the underlying variety of control issues, spanning from low-level control to decisional (and behavioral) autonomy [7]. Among others, a crucial knowledge engineering problem is the lack of a generally accepted modeling methodology entailing many potential back-and-forth (re)work over models and control parameters before defining the proper control configuration.

Some attempts to connect AI and Robotics environments have been made. For instance, ROSPlan [2] has been proposed

as a unique integrated solution for PDDL-based planners to be smoothly deployed in ROS architectures [8] also with planning techniques specifically used for human-robot interaction [9]. Robotics experts can easily connect their ROS-based modules to any (supported) PDDL-planner but there is no support to define planning specifications. So, roboticists are left alone in managing a knowledge planning modelling. Several timeline-based planning frameworks such as, e.g., EUROPA [10] and APSI-KEEN [11], provide knowledge engineering support for planning. But none of them provides structured support for deployment of robotic applications. In general, all those solutions require robotic experts to have some expertise in planning specification. A first solution addressing this issue has been proposed in [7] to facilitate the interaction between AI and Robotics experts. Yet, a domain expert may have difficulties in approaching this kind of solutions. A *Domain expert* is usually responsible for the definition of the tasks and overall goals of a robotic system, while other actors have responsibility on more specific aspects, i.e., a *planning expert*, with models to provide robust A.I. planning features, and a *robotic expert*, responsible for implementing robot operations.

This abstract presents a novel software tool, called “Tool foStEriNg Ai plaNning in roboTics” (TENANT) [12], addressing the needs of Domain Experts to set goals, defining tasks and set operational constraints notwithstanding the intrinsic complexity required at planning and robotics level. TENANT is a general purpose tool that can be deployed for addressing multiple applications/domains and can be easily integrated with other knowledge engineering tools such as, e.g., ROS-TiPIEx [7] and Planning and Scheduling software framework, e.g., PLATINUm [13]. TENANT specifically focuses on Human-Robot Collaboration and allows domain experts to specify *collaborative models* and thus describe *tasks* needed to achieve desired (productive) goals. Tasks can be either compound or simple (i.e., further structured in other sub-tasks) and are characterized by specific configurations/properties relevant for their execution, like e.g., collaborative modalities, or assignment preferences specifying who is actually in charge of performing a certain (sub)task. Furthermore, TENANT supports the definition of *operational constraints* such as, e.g., temporal synchronizations or precedence constraints in order to characterize the correct execution of the resulting production/control flow. Given a complete (and correct)

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collaborative model, TENANT can automatically generate a suitable *planning model* that can be used to feed a Planning & Scheduling system thus enabling intelligent (collaborative) robot behaviours.

The developed tool is validated on a concrete (and realistic) HRC production process derived from an EU-funded research project (Sharework¹). The validation shows the feasibility of the tool and the underlying engineering methodology. TENANT supports the correct design of the considered collaborative process and the automatic synthesis of a valid (timeline-based) planning specification, completely abstracting from the syntactic features of the underlying planning formalism.

II. A TOOL FOSTERING AI PLANNING IN ROBOTICS

The methodology behind TENANT can be described as follows: (i) a domain expert defines a collaborative process in terms of tasks, operational requirements and possible *assignments* (some tasks should be performed by the human only, some by the robot only and some by both); (ii) a planning model *template* for the task planning specification is defined by a planning expert to model generic tasks and operational requirements as an abstraction of task planning (e.g., a set of state variables and temporal constraints) and; (iii) an automatic tool *instantiates* the template of the task planning specification into a planning model. TENANT implements such methodology constituting an automatic tool to encode the given production description in a fully instantiated (timeline-based) planning specification. An automated planning software, like e.g., PLATINUM, is then able to use such specification as input, control the cobot and guarantee the achievement of the production objective (defined by a domain expert). Without such automatic tool, this process requires a non-trivial effort by domain experts and planning engineers to build a valid and correct planning model representing the production process and the tasks a human and/or a robot can perform.

TENANT defines a shared modelling process supporting both domain experts and planning engineers during the design and definition of the collaborative process, guiding the planning specification generation process and fostering production quality as well as improving its productivity. Three main steps are supported to facilitate intelligent human-robot coordination through the deployment of task planning technologies that are: (i) *template definition*; (ii) *process and task definition* and; (iii) *planning model generation*.

The proposed framework is implemented as a web-based application providing domain experts with an interactive graphical environment to incrementally define process descriptions. Input information is persistently stored into a local database for successive refinement and updates of process descriptions. As soon as a process description is complete, TENANT allows a domain expert to generate (as output) a complete planning specification, coherent with the given process description. A *planning expert* can then use the generated model as input for a planning and scheduling software. TENANT promotes

process definition reusability and thus facilitates task planning model adaptation in case of changes of production needs (tasks and/or operational requirements). It offers an access point to task planning technologies for domain experts, presenting a specific vision on the overall system and allowing them to define information closer to their expertise. In this way, domain experts and planning experts do not need to build strong cross-competencies or to have long iterative interaction to build a shared model. A structured modeling process indeed prevents misunderstandings/errors and facilitates *knowledge sharing*.

For each task, a domain expert can initially define the task's name and its collaborative modality. Then, a sequence of subtasks can be defined to build its actual composition. For each subtask, the user must specify its type (e.g., object manipulation or pick and place), which agent is supposed to perform it (i.e., robot, human or no preference) and the involved positions in the working area.

The screenshot shows a web-based interface titled "Work-cell Operations". Under the "Production Process" section, there are four task entries, each with a "Delete" button:

- First - Independent**: Task "PickAndPlace" (From position 1, Human) and subtask "Manipulation" (In position 3, Robot).
- Second_a - Supportive**: Task "Manipulation" (In position 1, Human/Robot).
- Second_b - Supportive**: Task "Manipulation" (In position 3, Human/Robot).

Below the tasks, there is a form to add a new subtask:

- Enter the name of the task:
- And its collaboration modality:
- Type of sub-task: From position to
- Which operator should perform it?:
- Buttons: "Add sub-task" and "Save task"

At the bottom, there is a "Select the number of positions" dropdown set to "4" and a "Next" button.

Fig. 1. Intermediate definition of a process with tasks and subtasks

Furthermore, within this domain, some constraints have to be taken into account when defining a subtask. For instance, a pick and place subtask can only be performed in Independent or Synchronous collaboration modality. Also, a task in Simultaneous or Supportive collaboration modality must be performed by both agents at the same time. Fig. 1 shows an excerpt of an assembly process consisting of four tasks.

III. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented TENANT, a novel software tool that facilitates domain experts in defining goals, tasks and operational constraints for the automatic generation of AI models for robot control. As future works, we plan to integrate TENANT in ROS-TiPIEx [7] to provide a comprehensive knowledge engineering tool for fostering A.I. and Robotics solutions and perform an analysis with domain experts to assess its usability and the required cognitive workload. Connecting this tool to suitable ontologies (see, e.g., [14]) can further facilitate the definition of models over well designed and formally defined set of concepts for HRC.

¹<http://www.sharework-project.eu>

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